

The Role of Family Support in Enhancing Higher Education Attainment: A Comparative Study across Socioeconomic Backgrounds

Dr. Gbenga Michael Adeyeye

Department of Education and Curriculum Studies University of Johannesburg

Dr. Nazreen Dasoo

Head of Department, Education and Curriculum Studies, University of Johannesburg

ABSTRACT: This study examines the impact of family support on the achievement of higher education, specifically exploring how socioeconomic status (SES) affects the accessibility and efficacy of financial, emotional, and intellectual assistance. Data were gathered using a qualitative research design, namely through in-depth interviews and reflective journals. The sample consisted of 90 people who were chosen to represent a range of socioeconomic backgrounds. The results indicate that students who come from families with both parents generally experience advantages in terms of stability and resources. However, the presence of socioeconomic gaps has a significant impact on the amount of support available to them. Families with a high socioeconomic status (SES) offer stronger financial and academic assistance, leading to improved educational results. Conversely, students from low SES homes face significant obstacles such as financial difficulties, limited access to academic resources, and insufficient school facilities. Parental participation has been identified as a crucial element in reducing the difficulties experienced by kids from low socioeconomic backgrounds. This emphasizes the importance of implementing policies that empower parents and tackle systematic disparities in education. This study highlights the significance of focused interventions in order to guarantee fair and equal access to resources and assistance for every student, hence fostering increased social mobility and educational achievement across socioeconomic disparities.

Keywords: Socioeconomic status, Family support, Academic performance, Higher education attainment, Parental involvement, Social mobility.

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1. Introduction

The attainment of higher education is commonly considered a significant component in determining individual and societal advancement. It functions as a crucial tool for accessing possibilities to improve one's social status, achieve economic security, and foster personal growth. Nevertheless, the process of acquiring a higher education degree is frequently filled with obstacles that can have a substantial impact on student achievements. Family support is a crucial aspect that significantly impacts educational achievement. Family support, which includes emotional, financial, and intellectual aid, is essential in influencing a student's capacity to negotiate the intricacies of higher education. This study

investigates the varying levels of familial assistance among several socioeconomic groups and its influence on higher education achievement.

Numerous studies have extensively demonstrated the importance of familial support in achieving educational success. Academic researchers have continuously emphasized the significance of a nurturing family environment in promoting academic motivation, resilience, and a feeling of inclusion among students (Alfaro et al., 2020). Family support can be demonstrated in various ways, such as providing financial assistance, offering emotional support, and actively participating in academic activities like helping with homework or attending school events. Nevertheless, the level and characteristics of this assistance frequently vary widely among various socioeconomic groups, resulting in discrepancies in educational achievements.

Socioeconomic status (SES) is a crucial factor that influences both the educational opportunities available to individuals and the achievements they achieve. According to Sirin (2021), it has an impact on the accessibility of resources, the quality of educational institutions, and the overall social context in which a student works. Families with higher socioeconomic status typically have more financial means, which enables them to offer their children superior educational materials, private tutoring, and other sorts of academic enrichment. In addition, these families may possess a greater amount of time and energy to actively participate in their children's education, creating a more supportive and favorable learning environment. Conversely, families with lower socioeconomic status may encounter difficulties in offering equivalent assistance due to financial limitations, rigorous employment timetables, and restricted availability of educational resources.

When correlation between familial assistance and the achievement of higher education gets increasingly intricate when taking into account the convergence of socioeconomic position and cultural influences. Family perceptions and involvement in schooling can be greatly influenced by cultural norms and expectations. For instance, several cultures place significant importance on the collective success of the family, perceiving the accomplishments of one family member as indicative of the honor and social standing of the entire family (González et al., 2019). Under such circumstances, families are more inclined to allocate resources towards their children's education, even if it involves substantial personal or financial hardship. In contrast, certain cultural contexts may prioritize urgent economic survival over long-term educational objectives, leading to a reduced focus on formal education.

This study aims to investigate the diverse and complex impact of family support on achieving higher education by conducting a comparative analysis across various socioeconomic backgrounds. This research, being qualitative in nature, enables a thorough exploration of the actual experiences of students and their families. It offers vital insights into how family dynamics impact educational achievements. By gathering their perspectives, this study seeks to illuminate the obstacles and possibilities that influence the educational paths of students from various socioeconomic backgrounds.

An examination of the current body of research indicates that students from wealthier socioeconomic backgrounds are more prone to receiving significant financial assistance from their families. This assistance can help alleviate the financial strain of tuition fees,

housing expenses, and other costs associated with pursuing higher education (Fosnacht & Dong, 2020). This financial assistance frequently goes beyond covering the direct expenses of school and includes a wider range of features, such as providing access to technology, study materials, and extracurricular activities that enhance the entire educational experience. Furthermore, families with a higher socioeconomic status (SES) are frequently more capable of offering guidance and mentorship, utilizing their own educational backgrounds and networks to assist their children in achieving their academic and professional goals.

Conversely, students belonging to poorer socioeconomic backgrounds may encounter substantial financial obstacles that hinder their ability to pursue higher education. The exorbitant fees associated with tuition, books, and living costs sometimes act as a barrier, prompting numerous students to seek part-time employment or depend on student loans to fund their education (Perna, 2021). The financial burdens might generate extra strain and restrict the amount of time and effort that students can allocate to their academic pursuits. In addition, the limited availability of financial resources may hinder students' ability to receive crucial academic support services, such as tutoring or counseling, which are vital for achieving academic success.

The emotional and psychological dimensions of familial support play an equally significant role in influencing educational achievements. A nurturing familial atmosphere can offer students the necessary support and drive to persist through the difficulties encountered in pursuing higher education (Wang & Heppner, 2020). When families encourage education and show confidence in their children's talents, it can help them develop a strong belief in themselves and a strong will to succeed academically. These factors are important indicators of academic achievement. In addition, receiving emotional support from family members helps alleviate the stress and anxiety commonly linked to the pressures of higher education, enhancing mental health and overall well-being.

Socioeconomic conditions also impact the capacity of families to provide emotional assistance. Families facing financial difficulties or other stressors may find it challenging to provide the same level of emotional support, as they may prioritize meeting essential requirements or tackling other challenges (Conger et al., 2021). Under such circumstances, students may experience a sense of seclusion or being overburdened without the support and motivation that could assist them in successfully managing the challenges of tertiary education. Understanding the wider social and economic circumstances in which family assistance functions is critical, as these factors can greatly influence the quality and effectiveness of the help offered.

Family engagement in educational activities and communication with educational institutions is a crucial aspect in achieving higher education. Studies indicate that parental engagement in education is linked to elevated academic performance, improved school attendance, and a heightened probability of pursuing further education (Hill & Tyson, 2021). When families actively participate in their children's education by attending parent-teacher conferences or helping with homework, they can strengthen the importance of education and promote academic achievement. Nevertheless, the extent of parental participation frequently differs according to socioeconomic class, with families from higher SES

backgrounds being more inclined to partake in these endeavors as a result of increased availability of information, resources, and leisure time.

In contrast, families with lower socioeconomic status may encounter obstacles to participation, such as linguistic hurdles, limited knowledge of the school system, or conflicting obligations (Cooper & Crosnoe, 2020). These obstacles can restrict their capacity to successfully assist their children in their education, perhaps resulting in lower academic performance and a decreased likelihood of achieving higher education. This emphasizes the necessity for educational institutions to acknowledge and tackle the many difficulties encountered by families from all socioeconomic backgrounds, promoting more comprehensive and encouraging environments for all kids.

Ultimately, the influence of familial assistance on achieving higher education is an intricate and diverse matter, intricately connected to socioeconomic elements. This study aims to investigate the diverse aspects of family support among individuals from different socioeconomic backgrounds, analyzing the impact of financial, emotional, and academic support on students' educational achievements. This project seeks to use a qualitative approach to understand and document the detailed experiences of students and their families. By doing so, it attempts to gain useful insights into how family dynamics influence higher education achievement. The results of this study have significant consequences for educational policies and practices, emphasizing the necessity for focused interventions that cater to the varied requirements of kids and their families, especially those from disadvantaged socioeconomic situations.

Problem Statement

Despite the widespread recognition of higher education as a critical tool for achieving upward social mobility and financial security, significant disparities in educational attainment persist across various socioeconomic classes. Family support, which includes financial, emotional, and intellectual aid, is crucial in determining a student's capacity to excel in higher education. Socioeconomic status (SES) frequently significantly impacts the accessibility and efficacy of this assistance. Students from higher socioeconomic status (SES) backgrounds generally have advantages such as more financial resources, increased parental involvement, and better access to academic opportunities. Students from lower SES backgrounds, on the other hand, frequently encounter obstacles such as financial constraints, limited access to high-quality educational resources, and insufficient parental support due to socioeconomic pressures.

These inequalities contribute to an expanding disparity in academic performance, as children from underprivileged origins have a lower likelihood of attaining higher education, hence perpetuating cycles of poverty and restricting upward social mobility. Although previous studies have examined the overall influence of family support on academic achievements, there is a dearth of comprehensive comprehension regarding how these dynamics manifest in various socioeconomic settings and the particular obstacles encountered by students from lower socioeconomic status (SES) backgrounds.

This study aims to fill this void by investigating the impact of family assistance on achieving higher education, specifically focusing on socioeconomic inequalities. The study

seeks to investigate the subjective experiences of students from diverse socioeconomic backgrounds in relation to various forms of family support and how these experiences impact their academic achievements. The findings will provide a vital understanding of the structural disparities that affect educational achievements and guide approaches to improving educational fairness and assistance for all students, irrespective of their socioeconomic situation.

The aim of this study is to investigate the influence of family support on attaining higher education, specifically by analyzing the disparities in financial, emotional, and academic support among students from different socioeconomic backgrounds and the potential effects of these differences on their academic achievements. The objective of the study is to examine the range and magnitude of family support offered to students from various socioeconomic backgrounds while they are pursuing higher education. Additionally, it seeks to assess the impact of financial, emotional, and intellectual support from family on their academic success, perseverance, and general welfare. Furthermore, this study aims to ascertain the obstacles faced by students from underprivileged socioeconomic backgrounds in obtaining sufficient family support and investigate the impact of these obstacles on their overall academic achievement.

To guide this investigation, the study asks the following questions: What differences exist in the type and amount of family support offered to students from various socioeconomic backgrounds? To what extent does the provision of financial, emotional, and academic assistance by families impact students' academic achievements, retention rates, and overall welfare in higher education? What are the particular challenges faced by students from underprivileged socioeconomic backgrounds in obtaining family support, and how do these challenges affect their academic performance in undergraduate education?

2. Literature Review

The impact of familial support on higher education has received much scholarly attention because of its substantial influence on students' academic success. Family support has a crucial role in students' academic achievement, emotional well-being, and overall educational outcomes as they navigate the difficulties of higher education. This literature review analyzes the current studies on the influence of family support on achieving higher education, specifically exploring how this support differs based on socioeconomic backgrounds and the consequences for educational fairness.

The correlation between family support and higher education attainment

Family support comprises a range of aid, such as financial, emotional, and academic support, which all contribute to a student's capacity to excel in higher education. Studies widely recognize the significance of familial support in achieving educational success, emphasizing its role in fostering academic drive, resilience, and perseverance among students (Garcia & Weiss, 2019). People commonly regard family support as a protective barrier against the difficulties and pressures associated with higher education. It offers students the necessary resources and motivation to overcome hurdles and attain academic accomplishments.

Financial aid is crucial for families, especially when it comes to higher education, where the prices for tuition, textbooks, and living costs can be significant. Studies have demonstrated that students who receive financial assistance from their families have a higher probability of enrolling in and successfully completing higher education programs (Perna & Finney, 2019). This assistance can mitigate the economic strain on students, enabling them to concentrate on their academic pursuits without the additional stress of working extensive hours to meet their financial obligations. Furthermore, the provision of financial assistance by families can augment students' opportunities to utilize resources such as technology, study materials, and extracurricular activities, all of which contribute to a more enhanced educational experience (Fosnacht & Dong, 2020).

Family involvement in higher education. An atmosphere characterized by familial support can cultivate a feeling of inclusion and personal effectiveness in students, which are significant indicators of academic achievement (Wang & Heppner, 2020). Students who perceive their families to be committed to their education and have confidence in their potential to succeed are more inclined to persist in the face of the difficulties encountered in higher education. Receiving emotional support from family members helps alleviate the stress and anxiety commonly linked to academic pressures, hence enhancing mental health and overall well-being (Conger et al., 2021).

Academic help provided by the family is critical for achieving higher education, as well as financial and emotional assistance. This support can manifest in diverse ways, encompassing aid with homework, motivation to achieve academic objectives, and engagement in educational endeavors such as parent-teacher meetings (Hill & Tyson, 2021). When families actively participate in their children's education, they may reinforce the importance of learning and assist kids in cultivating the necessary skills and behaviors for academic success. Nevertheless, families' own educational experiences and knowledge of the higher education system frequently shape the extent of academic assistance they offer (Cooper & Crosnoe, 2020).

Socioeconomic status and family support.

Socioeconomic status (SES) is a crucial determinant of the type and level of family assistance in higher education. Families with better socioeconomic status generally own more significant financial means, allowing them to offer more substantial financial assistance to their children (Sirin, 2021). Furthermore, these families are more inclined to possess the necessary time and vitality to actively participate in their children's education, providing both scholastic support and emotional motivation. Consequently, students from higher socioeconomic status (SES) backgrounds frequently have access to a more comprehensive support structure that enhances their achievement in higher education.

Conversely, families with lesser socioeconomic status may have substantial obstacles when it comes to offering assistance to their children in pursuing higher education. Financial limitations pose a major obstacle for these families, as they may face difficulties in affording tuition fees, purchasing textbooks, and meeting other educational obligations (Perna, 2021). Students from lower socioeconomic origins often experience financial challenges that can result in heightened stress levels and a higher probability of having to work while pursuing their studies. This, in turn, can negatively impact their

academic performance. Moreover, the constrained financial means of these families may impede students' ability to avail themselves of academic support services, such as tutoring or counseling, that have the potential to improve their educational achievements (Gaddis, 2019).

Socioeconomic issues also impact the emotional and psychological dimensions of family support. Households experiencing financial difficulties or other sources of strain may have less capacity to offer the necessary emotional assistance that is vital for the academic achievement of students (Conger et al., 2021). Parents who work several jobs or face financial instability may have limited time and energy to provide support or have meaningful discussions regarding their children's academic development. Students may experience feelings of isolation and reduced motivation in the absence of emotional support, particularly when they are already grappling with the challenges of higher education (Kuo et al., 2020).

Socioeconomic class also influences the level of academic support families provide. Research shows a correlation between parental involvement in school and improved academic performance, as well as a higher likelihood of pursuing post-secondary education (Hill & Tyson, 2021). Nevertheless, families hailing from lower socioeconomic status (SES) backgrounds may encounter obstacles when it comes to engagement, such as language challenges, limited knowledge about the educational system, or conflicting obligations that consume their time (Cooper & Crosnoe, 2020). These obstacles can restrict their capacity to successfully assist their children in their education, perhaps resulting in lower academic performance and a decreased likelihood of achieving higher education.

Cultural influences and familial assistance

Cultural considerations, alongside socioeconomic position, exert a substantial influence on the nature and scope of family support in higher education. Cultural norms and expectations can influence families' perspectives and involvement in education, as well as the forms of assistance they provide to their children. For instance, several cultures place significant importance on the collective success of the family, perceiving the accomplishments of one family member as indicative of the honor and social standing of the entire family (González et al., 2019). Under such circumstances, families may have a higher propensity to allocate resources towards their children's education, even if it entails substantial personal or financial hardship.

In contrast, certain cultural contexts may prioritize urgent economic survival over long-term educational objectives, leading to a reduced focus on formal education. These disparities can result in variations in the amount of assistance given by families, as well as the demands placed on pupils in terms of their academic achievements (Chao & Kanatsu, 2020). Gaining insight into these cultural variables is essential for cultivating a full understanding of how familial assistance impacts higher education achievement.

Educational policy refers to the set of principles and guidelines that govern the educational system. It encompasses the rules and regulations that shape the curriculum, teaching methods, and overall structure of schools. Family support, on the other hand, refers to the assistance and resources provided to families in order to encourage their children's educational success.

The variations in family support among different socioeconomic and cultural origins have substantial consequences for educational policy. To ensure equitable access to academic support for all students in higher education, a comprehensive strategy is necessary to cater to the varying demands of families from diverse backgrounds. Educational institutions can effectively mitigate the disparity by offering supplementary assistance services, such as monetary assistance, educational guidance, and psychological support, specifically targeting students from socioeconomically disadvantaged households (Gaddis, 2019). Furthermore, implementing policies that encourage family involvement and engagement in education might enhance the support networks that are crucial for student achievement (Hill & Tyson, 2021).

Socioeconomic and cultural factors profoundly shape the intricate and diverse impact of family support on achieving higher education. Students from higher socioeconomic origins typically receive greater financial, emotional, and intellectual assistance, whereas those from lower socioeconomic backgrounds encounter severe obstacles that impede their educational achievements. To address these inequalities, we need a comprehensive strategy that considers the diverse needs of students and their families, prioritizing equal opportunities for all students to thrive in higher education.

3. Methodology

This section provides an overview of the research design, how participants were chosen, the techniques used to collect data, and the procedures used to analyze the data in order to investigate how family support contributes to higher education achievement among individuals from various socioeconomic backgrounds. Due to the intricate nature and profoundness of the research subject, a qualitative methodology was considered the most suitable in order to effectively capture the subtle experiences and viewpoints of students and their families.

Research Design

This study used a qualitative research approach to examine the characteristics and influence of familial assistance on the achievement of higher education. The use of qualitative research is ideal for this study since it enables a thorough examination of participants' real-life experiences, offering a comprehensive and detailed understanding of how family dynamics impact scholastic achievements. The study employs a phenomenological methodology, which centers on comprehending the fundamental nature of participants' encounters with familial assistance throughout their pursuit of higher education. This method is successful in collecting the subjective experiences of students from various socioeconomic backgrounds and how these experiences influence their educational paths.

Selection of Participants

The participants for this study were chosen by purposive sampling, a method that entails selecting individuals who are highly likely to offer pertinent and comprehensive information about the topic being studied. The selection criteria for participants encompassed the following: (1) being a present or recent alumnus of a tertiary educational

institution, (2) originating from diverse socioeconomic circumstances, and (3) encountering different degrees of familial assistance throughout their academic pursuit.

In order to guarantee a varied and inclusive sample, 90 residents of Ogbomoso North and Ogbomoso South Local Government Authorities were selected from several institutions of higher learning, including universities and technical colleges situated in both local government authorities. The study sought to ensure a fair and equal representation of students from high, middle, and poor socioeconomic backgrounds. Socioeconomic status was assessed by considering variables such as household income, parental educational attainment, and occupational status.

The study had a sample size of 90 participants, with an equal distribution of 30 students from each of the three socioeconomic categories (high, middle, and low). The sample size was selected to facilitate a thorough investigation of the research inquiries while ensuring feasibility in terms of data gathering and analysis.

Methods for Collecting Data

The data were gathered via semi-structured, in-depth interviews, which are particularly suitable for qualitative research since they offer flexibility in investigating participants' perspectives while also ensuring that important subjects are addressed. The interview guide was constructed using the study's research questions and objectives. It consisted of open-ended questions intended to elicit comprehensive comments regarding participants' experiences with family support throughout their higher education journey.

The interview questions were around the following topics:

The level and scope of financial, emotional, and academic assistance provided by family members. The perceived influence of this assistance on the academic achievement, persistence, and general welfare of the participants. The difficulties encountered in obtaining sufficient familial assistance, particularly for individuals hailing from disadvantaged socioeconomic circumstances. Participants' reflections on the impact of their family's support on their school achievement and future goals. The interviews were done in a secluded and cozy environment to foster honesty and frankness. Every interview had a duration ranging from 60 to 90 minutes and was recorded in audio format with the participants' explicit permission. In order to maintain precision, the interviews were transcribed exactly as they were spoken, and participants were provided with the chance to examine and authorize their transcripts.

Alongside interviews, the study also employed reflective journals, in which participants were instructed to record their thoughts and experiences concerning family support throughout the study period. The inclusion of these journals enhanced the interview data by providing supplementary context and profound insights, facilitating a more comprehensive comprehension of the individuals' experiences.

Data analysis

The process of data analysis was carried out using thematic analysis, which is a systematic approach involving the identification, examination, and documentation of recurring patterns (themes) within the data. The decision to utilize thematic analysis was based on its exceptional ability to emphasize both the shared and distinct aspects of participants' experiences while also facilitating a comprehensive investigation into the elements that impact the achievement of higher education.

The analysis methodology comprised the subsequent steps:

Data Familiarization: The researcher engaged in a process of carefully reviewing and analyzing the interview transcripts and reflective diaries in order to get a comprehensive comprehension of the data. Observations and first impressions were documented at this stage.

Generating Initial Codes: The data were methodically categorized by finding sections of text that were pertinent to the study inquiries. The process of coding was carried out manually, with the codes being categorized based on various factors of family support and its influence on the achievement of higher education.

Theme identification: The codes were further categorized into more comprehensive themes that encompassed the fundamental trends in the data. Themes were derived from the frequency of particular experiences, the importance of specific sorts of assistance, and the problems stated by individuals from various socioeconomic backgrounds.

Theme review: The identified themes underwent a thorough evaluation and adjustment process to guarantee their accuracy in representing the data and relevance to the research questions. This procedure entailed verifying the themes by comparing them with the original facts to ensure their pertinence and logical consistency.

Establishing and Designating Themes: After the themes were determined, they were precisely defined and given specific names. Every theme was followed by an elaborate explanation, which included instances from the data to demonstrate its importance.

Completing the report entailed composing a comprehensive narrative that incorporated the identified themes and directly addressed the study questions and objectives. Incorporated throughout the research were verbatim statements from participants, serving to substantiate the findings and offer a comprehensive and intricate depiction of their encounters.

Ethical considerations

The study was conducted with a strong emphasis on ethical issues, especially due to the sensitive nature of the topic and the potential vulnerability of the participants. The study complied with the ethical norms established by the appropriate institutional review boards.

Prior to conducting the interviews, all participants were given informed permission, which ensured that they had a comprehensive understanding of the study's objectives, methods, and their entitlements as participants. The participants were guaranteed the secrecy of their comments, and any identifying information was made anonymous in the transcripts and final report.

In addition, the participants were notified of their entitlement to withdraw from the study at any point without facing any consequences. The researcher also took into consideration the emotional repercussions that revealing personal and perhaps difficult family experiences could have on participants and offered recommendations for counseling services if necessary.

Reliability and meticulousness

In order to guarantee the reliability and thoroughness of the investigation, many measures were implemented:

Triangulation was employed by utilizing many data sources, including interviews and reflective diaries, to validate the findings and enhance the overall comprehension of the research subject.

Member Checking: Participants were provided with the chance to examine and authorize their interview transcripts in order to verify their accuracy and legitimacy.

Reflexivity: The researcher diligently kept a reflexive notebook throughout the study, recording personal reflections and potential biases that could impact the research process. Thick Description: Elaborate explanations of the research backdrop, participants, and findings were given to improve the applicability of the study's conclusions to different environments.

Themes, Codes, and Data Analysis for the Study

Due to the qualitative nature of this study, it is crucial to focus on the themes, codes, and data analysis process. These elements will play a vital role in identifying patterns, comprehending the lived experiences of participants, and interpreting the findings within the framework of existing research on the impact of family support on higher education achievement. The data supplied above offers a substantial basis for constructing a thorough coding system and conducting a theme analysis.

Themes

The data presented has revealed the following main themes:

The influence of family structure on educational outcomes:

This theme examines the impact of dual parental involvement in a family on a child's access to resources, time, and energy, which subsequently affects their educational development and outcomes.

Socioeconomic inequalities and the availability of resources:

This issue explores the impact of socioeconomic status (SES) on the accessibility of financial, emotional, and intellectual assistance, specifically examining the inequalities in resources and opportunities across families of high, middle, and low SES.

The impact of parental involvement on academic performance:

This issue explores the impact of parental participation on children's education, specifically in households facing economic disadvantages, and its relationship with academic achievement.

Obstacles to Education for Underprivileged Students:

This subject emphasizes the difficulties encountered by students from underprivileged families, such as limited financial support, restricted access to educational materials, and the influence of socioeconomic issues on academic achievement.

Impact of Socioeconomic Factors on Academic Decision-making and Achievement:

This theme examines the impact of several socioeconomic circumstances, including family history, financial difficulties, and resource availability, on students' academic decisions, career choices, and overall achievement.

Programming codes

The subsequent codes were formulated to capture distinct facets of each theme during the analysis:

Structure of the family:

Dual-parent domicile

Household headed by a single parent

Prospects for financial gain

Social mobility refers to the ability of individuals or groups to move up or down the social ladder in terms of their socioeconomic status. It measures the extent to which people can improve their social status.

Socioeconomic status (SES):

High socioeconomic status (SES)

Middle socioeconomic status

Low socioeconomic status (SES)

Level of income

Parents education and occupation

Parental participation:

Assistance with academic endeavors

Psychological assistance

Financial support

School engagement

Literacy performance

Barriers to Education:

Financial assistance

Access to resources

Quality of education

Teacher qualifications
Infrastructure

Socioeconomic Influences:

Study choices
Career decisions
Health
Peer influence
Entrepreneurial activities
Data Analysis

The data analysis method includes the following steps:

Data Familiarization:

The data provided was evaluated numerous times to acquire a good grasp of the subject. Notes were made on crucial elements that aligned with the research objectives.

Coding:

The data was methodically coded using the established codes. Each part of the text was labeled with one or more codes that captured the core of the material. For example, references to the impact of a two-parent home on educational results were classified under "family structure" and "two-parent household."

Theme Development:

The codes were then arranged into bigger themes that mirrored the primary concerns being researched. For instance, the codes linked to financial, emotional, and academic assistance from parents were combined under the theme "Parental Involvement and Academic Performance."

Pattern Identification:

Patterns were observed within and across the themes. For example, it was noted that adolescents from low SES homes who got substantial parental participation often demonstrated academic improvement, despite minimal resources.

Analysis within a certain context:

The results were placed in the wider context of the existing research on family support, socioeconomic status (SES), and educational achievements. The investigation examined the interplay between these factors in shaping academic achievement and explored alternative approaches to mitigate inequalities in resource access.

Explanation:

The last stage involved analyzing the themes in relation to the study's research questions. As an illustration, the topic "Socioeconomic Disparities and Access to Resources" was employed to address inquiries regarding the impact of socioeconomic status on both family assistance and educational achievement.

Comprehensive Examination Influence of Family Structure on Academic Achievements:

The evidence indicates that children raised in households with two parents experience advantages in terms of increased resources, including financial and emotional support, which in turn leads to improved academic performance. Having two parents present typically results in more secure financial circumstances, enabling more time and effort to be allocated towards the child's growth and progress. Nevertheless, the division between social classes within these households also plays a role in exacerbating inequality, since families with greater socioeconomic status are able to utilize their resources more efficiently.

Socioeconomic inequalities and the availability of resources:

Socioeconomic status largely influences access to resources necessary for educational attainment. Families with a high socioeconomic status (SES) are more capable of affording high-quality education, extracurricular activities, and academic support. On the other hand, families with a low SES sometimes face financial limitations, resulting in a disparity in educational opportunities. The evidence suggests that improving the quality of education in low-income neighborhoods and guaranteeing equal access to food and medical care can help reduce these inequalities.

The correlation between parental involvement and academic performance:

Parental participation is essential, especially in families with financial disadvantages. The data references studies that demonstrate that active parental involvement can result in enduring academic advantages, such as improved literacy proficiency and increased educational achievement. This engagement serves as a form of reparation for certain drawbacks experienced by children in low socioeconomic status (SES) families, underscoring the significance of promoting and supporting parental involvement in school.

Obstacles to Education for Underprivileged Students:

Individuals from underprivileged origins have numerous obstacles, such as limited access to financial aid, inadequate infrastructure, and insufficiently skilled educators. These problems exacerbate a substantial disparity in educational attainment among various areas and populations. The research highlights the necessity of implementing focused interventions, such as financial assistance and enhanced educational resources, to provide support for these learners.

Impact of Socioeconomic Factors on Academic Decision-making and Achievement:

Socioeconomic factors, such as familial background, financial difficulties, and peer influence, have a significant impact on students' academic decisions and achievements (Adeyeye, 2023). The research indicates that kids from socioeconomically disadvantaged homes are more prone to facing obstacles that impede their academic achievement, such as limited availability of computers and educational resources, exposure to violence, and

food insecurity. It is crucial to consider and tackle these concerns in order to advance educational fairness.

In conclusion, the data analysis reveals the intricate relationship between family structure, socioeconomic level, and educational outcomes. It demonstrates that although homes with two parents often offer greater assistance for a child's growth, socioeconomic inequalities worsen the gap between social classes, resulting in unequal educational prospects. Parental engagement, particularly in families with low socioeconomic status (SES), is crucial for achieving academic achievement. However, learners from disadvantaged households encounter substantial obstacles that necessitate specific interventions. To address these discrepancies, it is important to expand access to resources, provide financial aid, and increase parental involvement. These measures can help reduce the gap in educational achievement and promote social mobility.

4. Discussion of Findings

The study's findings offer a thorough comprehension of the intricate relationship between family support, socioeconomic status (SES), and the achievement of higher education. In-depth interviews and reflective journals provide valuable qualitative data that sheds light on the impact of these factors on students from various backgrounds' academic experiences and achievements. This debate will examine the main issues that arose from the analysis and their implications for educational policy, practice, and future research.

The impact of family structure on academic achievement

This study's key discovery is the impact of family composition, namely the presence of dual parents in a residence, on a child's academic achievements. The findings indicated that students from households with both parents typically encountered more consistent and nurturing surroundings, which had a positive impact on their academic achievements and overall welfare. Two parents' collective financial, emotional, and temporal resources were primarily responsible for the stability.

Nevertheless, the study also emphasized that the advantages linked to two-parent homes were not evenly distributed throughout all socioeconomic classes. Even in households with two parents, families from higher socioeconomic origins were able to utilize their resources more efficiently to assist their children's education. This included facilitating access to superior educational resources, supplementary activities outside of the regular curriculum, and scholastic mentoring, all of which are necessary for achieving academic excellence. Conversely, households with two parents in lower socioeconomic status (SES) groups saw considerable difficulties in offering equivalent support as a result of financial limitations.

This discovery emphasizes the necessity for focused treatments that take into account both the composition of the family and socioeconomic status. While it is critical to prioritize the promotion of stable family environments, policies must also address the economic inequalities that hinder the efficacy of family assistance in homes with lower socioeconomic status (SES). Educational institutions can help narrow this disparity by

providing supplementary resources and support services to students from economically disadvantaged two-parent households.

Disparities in socioeconomic status and resource availability.

The study confirmed the well-documented correlation between socioeconomic level and the availability of educational resources. Individuals from higher socioeconomic status (SES) backgrounds consistently indicated having more extensive availability of financial, academic, and emotional assistance, which contributed to their achievements in higher education. This access resulted in improved academic achievement, increased retention rates, and a more favorable overall educational experience.

In contrast, students from lower socioeconomic status (SES) families had substantial obstacles in obtaining equivalent levels of assistance. Participants frequently mentioned financial restrictions as a reoccurring theme, expressing challenges in meeting the costs of tuition, textbooks, and other necessary educational resources. The financial difficulties frequently compelled students to do part-time employment, which hindered their capacity to concentrate on their studies and had an adverse effect on their academic achievement.

Additionally, the research discovered that students from low socioeconomic status (SES) backgrounds had a lower probability of accessing academic support services, such as tutoring and counseling. These services are essential for successfully navigating the challenges of higher education. The absence of these resources intensified the difficulties experienced by these pupils, resulting in diminished academic performance and, in certain instances, increased rates of leaving school prematurely.

These findings emphasize the immediate necessity for strategies that target the resource inequalities among pupils from high and low socioeconomic status (SES). Promoting educational equity requires guaranteeing fair access to educational resources, including financial aid, academic support services, and cheap study materials.

The impact of parental involvement on academic performance.

Scholars have identified parental participation as a crucial element in the academic achievement of pupils, particularly those from economically challenged households. The research found a link between improved academic results and active parental participation in education, which includes emotional support, academic mentoring, and engagement in school activities.

Parental participation frequently served as a mitigating factor for students from low socioeconomic status (SES) backgrounds, helping to offset the limited financial means they had. Participants who indicated a significant degree of parental engagement also expressed increased academic drive, improved academic performance, and a heightened belief in their own ability to succeed. This discovery aligns with previous research, indicating that parental engagement might serve as a safeguard, shielding adolescents from the adverse consequences of socioeconomic deprivation.

However, the research also revealed that the parents' educational backgrounds and familiarity with the higher education system had an impact on parental engagement. Parents who had attained higher levels of education showed a greater propensity to employ successful participation tactics, such as assisting with homework or maintaining communication with teachers. Conversely, parents who have lesser educational attainment frequently encounter difficulties in offering equivalent academic assistance, although they are emotionally supportive.

This discovery emphasizes the significance of enabling parents, especially those from poor socioeconomic status backgrounds, to actively participate in their children's education in a more efficient manner. Educational institutions can significantly contribute to this endeavor by providing workshops, tools, and support networks that assist parents in navigating the educational system and acquiring the necessary skills to effectively support their children's academic progress.

Obstacles to Education for Underprivileged Students

The study found various primary obstacles to education encountered by learners from underprivileged backgrounds, such as budgetary constraints, limited availability of high-quality educational materials, and insufficient infrastructure. The obstacles were most evident in rural regions and low-income communities, where schools frequently lacked the financial resources required to deliver a top-notch education.

Individuals from these particular demographics expressed difficulties with antiquated educational materials, excessively populated learning environments, and restricted availability of technological resources, all of which impeded their academic achievements. In addition, the study revealed that these kids frequently faced a shortage of competent teachers and academic support resources, which worsened the educational inequalities among various socioeconomic groups.

The restrictions had a noticeable effect on underprivileged students' academic achievement, with many of them experiencing worse grades, increased rates of dropping out, and reduced educational ambitions. The results indicate that resolving these systemic problems necessitates a comprehensive strategy, encompassing augmented financial resources for schools in economically disadvantaged regions, enhanced teacher education, and a broader availability of academic support services.

Moreover, the study emphasizes the significance of establishing secure and fair learning settings that promote academic achievement for every student, irrespective of their socioeconomic status. This involves equipping educational institutions with the necessary resources and facilities to enable effective instruction and learning.

The Impact of Socioeconomic Factors on Academic Decision-making and Achievement

The study demonstrated that socioeconomic factors had a substantial influence on students' academic decisions and achievements. Socially disadvantaged students were more likely to say that financial worries, familial responsibilities, and peer pressure influenced their course choices, study methods, and career expectations.

Many low socioeconomic status (SES) students face the obstacle of having to financially support their household or feeling compelled to start working at a young age. This hinders their ability to follow specific academic pathways or dedicate time to extracurricular activities that could enrich their educational journey. This often leads to a decrease in academic and professional opportunities, thereby perpetuating the cycle of socioeconomic deprivation.

Conversely, students from higher socioeconomic status (SES) backgrounds indicated that they had greater autonomy to investigate a broader array of academic interests and pursue long-term professional aspirations. Economic pressures did not hinder their family's financial security, allowing them to prioritize their education with flexibility.

The results indicate that interventions aimed at assisting students from low socioeconomic backgrounds should encompass not just monetary assistance but also guidance in job selection and academic counseling, which enable students to make well-informed choices regarding their education and future professional paths. Facilitating chances for these students to participate in extracurricular activities, internships, and other enrichment programs can also contribute to expanding their academic and vocational perspectives.

5. Policy and practice implications

The results of this study have important consequences for educational policy and practice. We recommend the following techniques to address the discrepancies in family assistance and academic achievements among various socioeconomic groups:

Promoting greater parental engagement:

Educational institutions should provide programs and resources that enable parents, especially those from low socioeconomic status (SES) backgrounds, to actively participate in their children's education. These could include instructional workshops on effective academic support strategies, guidance on navigating the educational system, and opportunities for parents to actively participate in school events.

Enhancing Resource accessibility:

Policies should prioritize the equitable provision of essential academic resources to all students, irrespective of their socioeconomic status. This includes financial assistance, academic support services, and cost-effective educational resources.

Enhancing Educational Facilities:

Investments in school infrastructure, especially in economically disadvantaged and remote places, are crucial for ensuring a secure and favorable learning environment. This encompasses the tasks of revising educational materials, enhancing the environment within classrooms, and guaranteeing the availability of technological resources.

Handling structural disparities:

To effectively tackle systemic inequalities in education, it is crucial to allocate specific funds to schools that cater to underprivileged areas, enhance teacher training programs, and implement activities that foster educational equity.

6. Conclusion

To summarize, this study emphasizes the critical importance of family support in achieving higher education, as well as the significant influence of socioeconomic level on the availability of resources, parental participation, and academic achievements. Students from higher socioeconomic status (SES) backgrounds have more support and opportunity, but those from lower SES origins encounter substantial obstacles that impede their educational achievements. To tackle these discrepancies, a comprehensive strategy is needed that includes strengthening parental engagement, expanding resource availability, upgrading school facilities, and tackling systemic inequities within the education system. By employing these tactics, educational institutions and policymakers can facilitate the development of a fair and nurturing environment for all students, irrespective of their socioeconomic status.

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